

This is possible! Assessing and benchmarking control performance

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Abstract: This contribution is a reflection of the collaboration between Nina and the Advanced Controls Technology Group at Eastman Chemical Company by John Cox. John is now a principal analytics engineer at Seeq Corporation.

Keywords: Control loop performance assessment, process control, industry relevance, plant-wide oscillations, grace and generosity.

Dear Nina,

As a member of Eastman's Advanced Controls Technology group in the late 1990s, I can still recall my excitement upon reading your early control loop performance and oscillation detection papers. Your research transformed our group's thinking from "How can we possibly assess and benchmark control loop performance across the company in an efficient way?" to "This is really possible!".

Our process control group had been interested for quite some time in control loop monitoring, but had not gotten further than historizing and reporting controller tuning parameter changes. Your research was technically strong, generously documented, and practical for industrial implementation. In short, it provided the foundation for a large-scale control loop performance monitoring application.

Those initial experiences then led to further interactions where you continued to provide industrially-relevant, technical contributions to our group: detection and diagnosis of plant-wide oscillations, publication of useful datasets, pointing us toward other pertinent research/researchers, and connecting us with a highly skilled, delightful intern (Margret Bauer).

Thank you for your invaluable contributions in making "what we had dreamed about" a reality: automated control loop performance monitoring for a large chemical company. Most importantly, thank you for the graceful and generous manner in which you did it - by being a truly nice, special and genuine person.

Congratulations on all you have accomplished and all the best for the future!

John Cox

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